

Breeding japonica lines with brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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Two BPH resistance genes (*Bph* 1 and *bph* 2) have been introduced from indica into japonica varieties by backcross breeding.

Kanto PL4 inherited the *Bph* 1 gene from Mudgo through F₃ 324 (Hoyoku/Mudgo//Kochikaze/3/IR781-1-94/4/Hoyoku). It has a high level of antixenosis similar to Mudgo and shows antibiosis similar to or slightly weaker. Kanto PL4 was registered in 1984 as Rice Norin PL3, a new germplasm of the *Bph* 1 gene, by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF).

Kanto PL5 was selected from the cross Asominori/IR1154-243//2*

Asominori. The early maturing IR1154-243 was a donor of the resistance gene *bph* 2. Kanto PL5 was registered in 1985 as Rice Norin PL4, the germplasm of *bph* 2.

The antibiosis of Kanto PL5 to BPH biotypes 1 and 2 is similar to or slightly weaker than that of IR1154-243. At every stage of growth, Kanto PL5 shows an inhibitive effect on BPH survival and population increase.

While Kanto PL4, with *Bph* 1, suffers severe damage from BPH biotype 2, the seedling growth of Kanto PL5 is not suppressed by nymphs of biotypes 1 and 2, but is attacked by biotype 3.

Kanto PL4 and Kanto PL5 are promising donors of BPH resistance for Japanese varieties. Lines with *Bph* 3 and *bph* 4 are being developed from Tukushibare/3/Tukushibare*3/Rathu Heenati//Tukushibare and Tukushibare*2/Babawee. ♀

Sources of resistance to green leafhopper (GLH)

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Heavy populations of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) caused hopperburn to rice varieties in Periyar district, Tamil Nadu, in 1984. Using the seedbox screening test in the greenhouse, 50 rice accessions were evaluated for GLH resistance. Ptb 33 was the resistant check and TN1 the susceptible check.

Rices were sown in seedboxes (60 × 40 × 10 cm) in 5 replications. Seven days after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 20/accession and infested with 4 to 5 third instars per seedling. When all plants in the susceptible check died, accessions were rated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice 0-9* scale.

Ten accessions (AD85001, BG367-4, IET7301, IET7303, IR54, IR58, IR62, IR64, TNAU 80042, TNAU 801793) had damage ratings of 1. IR62 and IR64, which were resistant to GLH, also have high levels of resistance to brown planthopper and whitebacked planthopper. ♀

Varietal reaction to thrips

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Fifty-one rice cultivars from AICRIP were screened for resistance to thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) in the field in Sep 1985. Each cultivar was planted in a 4-m-long row at 20- × 15-cm spacing. One row of susceptible check TN1 was planted for every 10 cultivars. The experiment was replicated twice and damage was evaluated by counting total leaves and damaged leaves in plants selected at random 30 d after sowing. The mean percentage of infestation was calculated and damage was scored: 0-10% infestation = resistant (R), 11-20% = moderately resistant (MR), 21-50% = moderately susceptible (MS), 51-100% = susceptible (S).

Nine cultivars showed good resistance, with damage ranging from 1.1 to 9.9% (see table). Another 28 exhibited moderate resistance, with damage ranging from 11 to 20%. ♀

Reactions of rice cultivars to thrips, Coimbatore, India.

Cultivar	Infestation (%)	Reaction
IET9705	1.1	R
IET9709	4.1	R
IET9719	5.8	R
IET9711	6.7	R
IET9727	7.6	R
IET9725	8.7	R
IET9723	9.3	R
IET9720	9.8	R
IET9710	9.9	R
IET9724	11.1	MR
IET9278	11.4	MR
IET9718	11.4	MR
IET8654	11.5	MR
IET8653	11.8	MR
IET9726	12.0	MR
IET9293	12.1	MR
IET8891	12.2	MR
IET7575	12.6	MR
IET9722	12.9	MR
IET9281	12.9	MR
IET8362	14.1	MR
IET9266	15.0	MR
IET9721	15.3	MR
Phalgun	15.8	MR
IET8892	16.3	MR
IET9266	16.4	MR
IET9702	16.4	MR
IET9265	16.6	MR
IET9273	16.7	MR
Rasi	17.3	MR
IET9704	17.8	MR
IET8394	18.0	MR

Table continued.

Cultivar	Infestation (%)	Reaction
IET9706	18.1	MR
IET9703	18.4	MR
IET9269	19.6	MR
IET9708	19.8	MR
IET9714	20.1	MR
IET9716	20.9	MS
IET9276	21.0	MS
IET8649	21.3	MS
IET9712	21.4	MS
IET9564	21.5	MS
IET9715	21.8	MS
IET9283	22.2	MS
IET9563	23.0	MS
IET9707	23.4	MS
IET9277	23.4	MS
IET9380	24.7	MS
IET9717	27.4	MS
IET9280	27.8	MS
IET9713	30.0	MS
TN1 check	61.7	S